

STITCHED NON-CRIMP FABRIC LAMINATES: FROM MANUFACTURING TO IN-PLANE PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

During the last decade an increasing interest can be observed in using complex textile fiber architectures (preforms) and resin infusion technologies to produce high performance civil aircraft FRP structures. In this context non-crimp fabrics (NCF) are very interesting concerning the goal of using large and cost effective semi-finished products. In addition, stitching is a very flexible method of interlinking different NCF shapes and of processing plane fiber configurations into complex, dry preforms. Furthermore, stitching can improve the mechanical out-of-plane properties due to the reinforcement with high performance threads in the thickness direction.

Although stitching is a relatively easy and flexible possibility to introduce additional reinforcements in the thickness direction the manufacturing of high quality stitched preforms means often a serious problem, because the influence of many parameters of the stitching process is not yet investigated satisfactorily. For example, the creation of a modified lock stitch, where the bobbin thread is completely at the bottom side and not pulled into the lower layers, depends - besides the configuration of the stitching machine - on a magnitude of various factors like composition and material of the preform to be stitched, stitching thread diameter and material, tension of the upper and lower thread, direction of stitching, etc..

Furthermore, the effects of varying stitching parameters on the in-plane mechanical properties of the composite are not clear. This is another problem, because in suitably designed laminates the in-plane fibers are primarily load bearing while the influence of additional stitches in the thickness direction can not be estimated in advance in a desired reliability. Against this background experiments were carried out in order to quantify the influence of varying stitching parameters on the in-plane mechanical behavior. Three different types of carbon fiber (HTA) NCF (types A, B and C) were stacked one upon each other to create a $[45/0/-45/0/90]_s$ layup. This preform configuration was stitched in the thickness direction using a modified lock stitch and E-glass fiber thread with varying stitch patterns and two different thread diameters (68 and 136 tex). After vacuum assisted resin infusion with an aerospace grade epoxy resin (RTM 6) macroscopic voids due to stitching could be observed. By means of micrographs it was realized that the orientations and distributions of cross sectional area of the voids in the thickness direction depend on the orientation and location of each individual layer of the laminate. The largest voids occurred always in the top and bottom layers whereas in the center of the laminate smaller voids were detected. Due to these voids disorientations of in-plane fibers emerged which cause changes in the in-plane mechanical properties. Quasi-static tests showed that the in-plane tensile modulus and the ultimate tensile strength are significantly affected by stitching depending on the stitch pattern, the thread diameter and the direction of stitching. In comparison to the unstitched NCF laminates maximum reductions of 29 % of the tensile modulus and 36 % of the ultimate tensile strength were found for a stitch density of 9.18 cm^{-2} using a 136 tex E-glass thread.

KEYWORDS: stitching, in-plane tensile modulus, non-crimp fabric, analysis of variance

INTRODUCTION

In the field of textile composites stitching takes a special position due to the use of an additional manufacturing step which is necessary for the introduction of a supplementary 3D fiber reinforcement into flat 2D fiber configurations [1, 6]. In most cases, stitching is used to join plane fiber structures

into complex 3D performs ready for liquid composite molding processes. Thereby, stitching primarily performs the task of realizing the demanded shape of the dry fiber structure without taking into consideration, that stitches are reinforcing elements in the thickness direction which affect mechanical properties of the composite. For example, it was observed that due to through-the-thickness stitching significant changes in mechanical properties perpendicular to the plane of the laminate can be achieved enabling to solve problems parallel to this weak direction of the composite. Some critical load cases of layered composite structures established in aircrafts for example are impact scenarios and crack propagation in a delaminated zone during operating conditions. Characteristic out-of-plane properties of composites are, among others, the strain energy release rates (G_{IC} , G_{IIC}) and it is published in the open literature that G_{IC} can be improved by more than a factor of 14 due to stitching in comparison to unstitched laminates [2]. Nevertheless, each stitch locally disturbs the in-plane fibers, which leads to changes in mechanical in-plane properties. Therefore, it is important to know how the mechanical in-plane behavior varies due to stitching. Nowadays, there is no doubt about the positive effects of additional stitching in the thickness direction of the laminate, but there are still contradictory statements concerning the influence of through-the-thickness stitching on the mechanical in-plane properties. A resume of different experimental studies on stitched composites is shown in [3] and it is clearly visible that it is impossible to appreciate changes in mechanical in-plane properties, such as tensile modulus and strength due to varying stitch densities for example. More effects have to be taken into account to understand the mechanical behavior of stitched laminates. Against this background a full factorial experimental test series was carried out, wherein some essential stitching parameters were varied. In this work the in-plane tensile modulus of unstitched and stitched NCF laminates was investigated in order to quantify the influence of stitching and to detect critical parameters in the sense of causing significant changes in in-plane tensile properties. Furthermore, micrographs of stitched and unstitched NCF were manufactured to characterize the stitch geometry in the various layers of the laminate. In addition, a Finite Elements (FE) model based on the results of the analysis of the stitch formation is presented to estimate the influence of stitching on the tensile modulus of some tested laminates. It was investigated to which extend it is possible to integrate the results of void formation into a unit cell model.

MATERIAL, STITCHING CHARACTERISTICS AND MANUFACTURING

Three different kinds of carbon fiber non-crimp fabrics (NCF) which are manufactured by Saertex and are denoted type A, B, C were stacked to generate a symmetrical $[+45/0/-45/0/90]_s$ laminate. To investigate the influence of stitching on the in-plane tensile properties a modified lock stitch which was generated using a 68 tex or 136 tex E-glass upper thread and a 68 tex E-glass lower thread was used. The stitch arrangement in terms of the spacing s and the pitch length p which determine the stitch density was varied between 3.3 mm and 5.0 mm (fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Definition of carbon fiber non-crimp fabric laminate lay-up and stitching parameters

Although it was additionally planned to vary the thread tension during the stitching process it had to be realized that it is impossible to define fixed levels of the upper and lower thread tension while adjusting the other parameters independently. For example, it was not possible to choose the same upper and lower thread tension for the different thread diameters because of different manufacturing characteristics of the yarn. On the other hand, a good loop formation independent of the choice of the other parameters could be realized by adjusting the thread tension suitably. Therefore, the thread tension is essential in the sense of creating satisfactory loop formations in the ABC NCF (fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Effect of varying upper stitching thread tension on the loop formation on the top (picture 1) and bottom (pictures 2 and 3) of a carbon fiber NCF configuration (136 tex E-glass thread)

Furthermore, the direction of stitching and testing was varied either parallel to x, i.e. parallel to the direction of the 0° fibers, or perpendicular, means parallel to y, respectively. According to this, a series of tensile tests was carried out with 32 different possibilities of choosing the stitching parameters.

The stitched dry preforms were infiltrated in a vacuum assisted resin infusion process with RTM 6 which is an aerospace grade epoxy resin produced by Hexcel Composites. For reference purposes unstitched ABC laminates were manufactured. After curing the average fiber volume fraction and thickness of the unstitched laminate was 52 % and 2.8 mm, respectively. According to the stitch density and the thread diameter the fiber volume fraction and the thickness of the stitched laminates varied significantly as the stitches restrict the compression of the NCF during the resin infusion. The higher the amount of stitches induced and the larger the thread diameter, the higher the thickness and, consequently, the lower the fiber volume fraction turns out. This results in a maximum reduction of the fiber volume fraction of more than 7.5 % at the maximum stitch density of 9.18 cm^{-2} using a 136 tex thread.

TESTING AND EVALUATION OF IN-PLANE TENSILE MODULUS

To determine quasi-static stress-strain curves of stitched and unstitched ABC laminates at least four specimens in one sample were tested in a 100 kN servohydraulic testing machine at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min in order to obtain a mean value and the corresponding standard deviation. The in-plane tensile modulus was evaluated as the secant modulus between 10 % and 50 % of the ultimate tensile strength [4, 5, 6]. A mean tensile modulus of the unstitched ABC laminate of $71,474 \text{ MPa} \pm 3,015 \text{ MPa}$ was evaluated parallel to x and $29,139 \text{ MPa} \pm 1,122 \text{ MPa}$ parallel to y, respectively. In the following paragraphs, all results are referred to the tensile modulus of the unstitched NCF laminate with respect to the testing directions parallel to x (denoted as U_x) or y (U_y ; tab. 1).

sample no.	tested parallel to	stitched parallel to	thread diameter [tex]	spacing s_i [mm]	pitch length p_i [mm]	no. of specimen [1]	mean tensile modulus [%]	standard deviation [%]
Ux	x	unstitched				6	100.0 ⁽¹⁾	4.2
1	x	x	68	5.0	5.0	4	92.0	2.9
2	x	x	68	5.0	3.3	4	89.4	1.9
3	x	x	68	3.3	5.0	3	89.4	2.8
4	x	x	68	3.3	3.3	4	92.6	2.4
5	x	x	136	5.0	5.0	3	86.3	2.0
6	x	x	136	5.0	3.3	4	86.0	3.7
7	x	x	136	3.3	5.0	4	94.3	2.3
8	x	x	136	3.3	3.3	4	86.4	2.0
9	x	y	68	5.0	5.0	3	92.6	4.1
10	x	y	68	5.0	3.3	4	96.1	4.0
11	x	y	68	3.3	5.0	3	89.5	2.9
12	x	y	68	3.3	3.3	4	95.3	7.6
13	x	y	136	5.0	5.0	4	88.8	4.6
14	x	y	136	5.0	3.3	4	76.4	2.8
15	x	y	136	3.3	5.0	4	98.7	10.3
16	x	y	136	3.3	3.3	4	85.0	1.5
Uy	y	unstitched				5	100.0 ⁽²⁾	3.9
17	y	x	68	5.0	5.0	4	87.9	5,1
18	y	x	68	5.0	3.3	4	95.1	3,5
19	y	x	68	3.3	5.0	4	87.9	5,6
20	y	x	68	3.3	3.3	3	85.4	9,0
21	y	x	136	5.0	5.0	4	86.3	3,8
22	y	x	136	5.0	3.3	4	88.3	4,3
23	y	x	136	3.3	5.0	4	85.7	4,6
24	y	x	136	3.3	3.3	3	71.0	3,6
25	y	y	68	5.0	5.0	4	100.3	3,9
26	y	y	68	5.0	3.3	4	103.9	4,0
27	y	y	68	3.3	5.0	4	92.9	3,8
28	y	y	68	3.3	3.3	4	90.3	5,7
29	y	y	136	5.0	5.0	4	89.0	3,6
30	y	y	136	5.0	3.3	3	83.2	3,4
31	y	y	136	3.3	5.0	4	91.7	3,7
32	y	y	136	3.3	3.3	4	89.0	6,8

⁽¹⁾: reference value 71,474 Mpa

⁽²⁾: reference value 29,139 MPa

Tab. 1: Tensile modulus of the stitched ABC laminates depending on the varied parameters normalized with respect to the tensile modulus of the unstitched laminate

It can be seen from tab. 1 that stitching in general reduces the in-plane tensile modulus compared to the unstitched ABC laminates. There are only two examples where a slight enhancement of the mean tensile modulus was detected within the scatter range (sample no. 25, 26). It is possible that with specific boundary conditions and stacking sequences of the laminate improvements due to stitching can be achieved. But it is too early to concretize this assumption in this phase of the investigations because of the lack of further experiments. The maximum reduction of 29 % (sample no. 24) was found at a maximum stitch density of 9.18 cm^{-2} ($s = p = 3.3 \text{ mm}$) and a thread diameter of 136 tex when tested perpendicular to the direction of stitching x.

It was observed that the in-plane tensile strength, in general, is also reduced by stitching in the thickness direction. The maximum decrease of about 36 % was detected perpendicular to the direction of stitching y at a stitch pattern $s = 5.0 \text{ mm}$ and $p = 3.3 \text{ mm}$ by using a 136 tex thread. For more information concerning the ultimate tensile strength the reader is referred to [8].

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE OF THE TENSILE MODULUS

A common statistical tool to quantify the influence of different parameters and their interactions is the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The objective is to define essential parameters and their combinations in the sense of significant changes of the tensile modulus compared to the unstitched ABC laminate. Due to an improved illustration letters and algebraic signs are introduced which describe the varied parameters and their adjustments. The chosen allocations and adjustments are shown in tab. 2.

parameter	testing direction parallel to		stitching direction parallel to		thread diameter [tex]		spacing [mm]		pitch length [mm]	
	x	y	x	y	136	68	5.0	3.3	5.0	3.3
allocation	A		B		C		D		E	
adjustment	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-

Tab. 2: Allocations of the varied parameters and their adjustments

As an example, the short form A+B-C+D-E- (sample no. 16) defines an ABC laminate, which is stitched parallel to y with a 136 tex thread by using spacing and pitch lengths of 3.3 mm each and tested parallel to x. Adjustments of single parameters and, additionally, interactions are investigated. For each interaction two different adjustments are possible as well. The interaction AB can be positive or negative and is defined by the product of the chosen adjustment of the parameters A and B. Both parameters A and B must be defined positive or negative in order to receive a positive interaction AB+. Therefore, the number of samples or adjustments m for each parameter and each interaction is 2. All m considered, there is a total number $m^{(total)}$ of 31. It is possible to quantify significant parameters and interactions because a full factorial test series was carried out. The evaluation starts, where all results are referred to the unstitched ABC laminates in tab. 1. It is assumed that the mean values of the tensile modulus parallel to x and y of the unstitched laminate define the reference values of 100 %. Therewith, the influence of stitching in relation to the unstitched laminates can be investigated. The total number n of stitched specimens is 121. It is abandoned to specify the general basics and the derivations of all formulas of an analysis of variance, which are published, e. g. in [7]. At the beginning a critical value $F^{(crit)}$ needs to be defined which depends on two degrees of freedom (DOF) k_1 and k_2 as well as a certain level of significance. In this work a level of significance of 95 % is assumed. The DOF k_1 and k_2 are defined as

$$k_1 = m - 1 = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad k_2 = (n - 1) - m^{(total)} = 89$$

k_1 describes the DOF to fix an adjustment while k_2 can be interpreted as a DOF concerning the error within groups. The critical value $F^{(crit)}$ can be evaluated based on these numbers together with corresponding tables given in [7].

$$F^{(crit)} = F_{(k_2)}^{(k_1)}(95\%) = F_{(89)}^{(1)}(95\%) \approx 3.96$$

The in-plane tensile modulus of each single specimen x_i of the whole test series is processed. At first the grand mean CF of all data is determined:

$$CF = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2}{n} = 976,516$$

In tab. 3 the used ANOVA formulas are listed for better illustration.

param. / interaction	DOF	$S^{(P/I)}$	$F^{(P/I)}$	$P^{(P/I)}$ [%]
(P/I)	k_1	$S^{(P/I)} = \frac{(\sum x_i^{(P/I+)})^2}{n^{(P/I+)}} + \frac{(\sum x_i^{(P/I)})^2}{n^{(P/I)}} - CF$	$F^{(P/I)} = S^{(P/I)} \cdot \frac{k_2}{S^{(error)}}$	$P^{(P/I)} = 100 \cdot \left[\frac{S^{(P/I)}}{S^{(total)}} - \frac{m}{S^{(total)}} \cdot \frac{S^{(error)}}{k_2} \right]$
$\left[\Sigma (P/I) \right]$	Σk_1	$S^{(sum)} = \sum_{m=1}^{m^{total}} S^{(P/I)}$	-	-
error	k_2	$S^{(error)} = S^{(total)} - S^{(sum)}$	-	$P^{(error)} = 100 \cdot \frac{n}{k_2} \cdot \frac{S^{(error)}}{S^{(total)}}$
total	$n-1$	$S^{(total)} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - CF$	-	$P^{(total)} = \sum P^{(P/I)} + P^{(error)} \equiv 100$

Tab. 3: Example of an ANOVA table for all parameters and interactions (P/I)

The ANOVA results of the in-plane tensile modulus of stitched ABC laminates are shown in tab. 4.

parameter / interaction	DOF	$S^{(P/I)}$	$F^{(P/I)}$	$P^{(P/I)}$ [%]
B	1	368	16.80	5.4
C	1	1,024	46.68	15.7
E	1	141	6.43	1.9
AB	1	257	11.72	3.7
AD	1	465	21.22	7.0
BC	1	88	4.02	1.0
CD	1	353	16.10	5.2
CE	1	591	26.94	8.9
DE	1	90	4.10	1.1
BCD	1	297	13.53	4.3
ABCE	1	138	6.31	1.9
(Σ insignificant)	(20)	(611)	(< 3.96)	(2.7)
error	89	1,952	-	41.3
total	120	6,375		100

Tab. 4: ANOVA table of the tensile modulus of stitched ABC laminates

A parameter or interaction is significant with respect to the in-plane tensile modulus, if the condition $F^{(P/I)} \geq F^{(crit)}$ can be applied. All insignificant parameters and interactions are not of prior interest and, therefore, resumed in the line “ Σ insignificant”. Finally, the percentages $P^{(P/I)}$ of all significant parameters, interactions and the error $P^{(error)}$ are determined. It is possible to clearly identify parameters which show a significant influence on the in-plane tensile modulus. The following conclusions can be drawn by analysing tab. 4:

1. The thread diameter (C) showed the most significant influence ($P^{(C)} = 15.7\%$). Using a small thread diameter (68 tex, C-) results in less reductions of the in-plane tensile modulus compared to a 136 tex stitching yarn. As the smaller the reinforcement in the thickness direction, the fewer the disorientations of the in-plane fibers, this result is coherent.
2. The second largest effect ($P^{(CE)} = 8.9\%$) was detected investigating the interaction between thread diameter and pitch length (CE). It can be concluded that the interaction CE has to be adjusted positively (CE+) to achieve a minimum effect on the in-plane tensile modulus. The adjustment of the pitch length (E-) is defined by taking conclusion 1 into account: a pitch length of 3.3 mm should be selected to realize a minimum reduction of the in-plane modulus.
3. The interaction of the direction of testing and the spacing (AD) was found as the third largest effect ($P^{(AD)} = 7.0\%$). Further investigations showed that (AD-) must be used to minimize the influence on the tensile modulus compared to the unstitched ABC laminate. Either should the direction of testing be parallel to x (A+) combined with a 3.3 mm spacing (D-), or the direction of testing should be parallel to y (A-) at a 5.0 mm spacing (D+).
4. 31 possible adjustments of parameters and combinations were investigated. 20 showed no significant influence on the in-plane tensile modulus (denoted as “Σinsignificant” in tab. 4).
5. A rather pronounced scatter range of the whole system exists. The given error value of $P^{(P/I)} = 41.3\%$ is to be interpreted as a statistical value of the overall scatter within samples of all investigated parameters and interactions. This number indicates a large variance in the whole system but does not represent the scatter in each tested sample. Reasons may be slight differences during the manufacturing process like e. g. in some cases restrictions of the void elongation due to the thread of the NCF. It could be seen on micrographs, that sometimes additional stitches were exactly at the same positions as the thread of the NCF, whereas in other cases the additional yarn was between two stitching lines of the NCF. This results in different void extensions within one stitch arrangement which may specifically affect the in-plane tensile modulus

GENERATION OF VOIDS DUE TO STITCHING

Stitches in the thickness direction of the NCF displace the in-plane fibers and generate macroscopic voids which are filled with the polymer matrix during infiltration. In fig. 3 a $[+45/0/-45/0/90]_s$ laminate was investigated which was stitched (parallel to x) using a 68 tex thread.

Fig. 3: Cross section of voids with respect to the xy-plane within the layers of a $[45/0/-45/0/90]_s$ NCF laminate due to stitching with an 68 tex E-glass thread parallel to the x-direction

To investigate the formation of voids within the layers of a multidirectional laminate due to stitching a number of micrographs parallel to the xy -plane were manufactured at different thickness locations. Based on the mean values (four measurements) of the void cross sections in each layer second order polynomial trend lines as shown in fig. 3 were approximated for each stitch arrangement by applying the least-square method. This procedure was chosen in order to determine the effect of void orientation and distribution of cross sectional area in the thickness direction of the ABC laminate on the in-plane fibers. A clear dependence of the void distribution on the location of each individual layer can be seen in fig. 3. The largest voids occurred in the layers forming the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate while the extension of the voids in the interior of the laminate were reduced to one-fourth. For more information the reader is referred to [6, 8]

Taking the results of the analysis of variance of the in-plane tensile modulus into account, especially conclusion 2 (a small pitch length and thread diameter to realize a minimum reduction in tensile modulus) the assumption is confirmed, that the in-plane void cross section due to stitching significantly influences the tensile stiffness. Using a small pitch length in general smaller voids are found in the outer A and C NCF compared to a stitch arrangement with a big pitch length at a constant spacing (cf. fig. 3). Each stitch interacts with the surrounding stitches and a large stitch density at a fixed spacing restricts the possibility of free void extensions which causes smaller void cross sections. Therefore, not only the stitch density is an essential parameter for affecting the formation of voids and the in-plane tensile stiffness, but rather the stitch arrangement defined by spacing and pitch length shows significant influence. This is a verification of the presumption that knowledge of the extension of voids due to stitching is very important in order to develop a reliable model of the mechanical behavior of stitched NCF laminates.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL TO PREDICT THE IN-PLANE TENSILE MODULUS

A linear elastic finite element model (ANSYS) was evaluated. The results of the void cross sections in different layers of the ABC laminate due to different stitch arrangements (cf. fig. 3) were taken into account. A representative unit cell depending on the stitch pattern was generated. An example of a unit cell for the stitch arrangement $s_1; p_1$ is shown in fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Partial illustration of generated volumes of a representative unit cell ($s_1; p_1$)

This unit cell was defined by the characteristics of the unstitched ABC laminate, the direction of loading, spacing, pitch length and the resulting voids due to a 68 tex thread stitched parallel to x . All volumes of the unit cells are constructed around a central stitch. The boundaries in the xy plane are defined by the spacing and pitch length dependent on the direction of stitching. Each void is modelled using isosceles triangles. The orientation of the void depends on the orientation of the fibres in each layer (cf. fig 3). It has to be taken into account that not only the central stitch but also surrounding voids may penetrate into the unit cell and, therefore, need to be considered. A 10-node tetrahedral solid element with orthotropic material properties (solid 92) was been chosen. The number of elements between 45,843 and 151,100 depends on the investigated stitching parameters. An uniaxial

unit displacement was applied parallel to the direction of loading on one side (e. g. the yz plane to determine the in-plane tensile modulus in x), whereas the displacements in this direction were fixed on the opposite side. Symmetry conditions were defined on the lateral planes (e. g. the xz plane for the modulus in x). The calculated nodal forces on the fixed side and the unit displacement were used in Hooke's Law to calculate the resulting tensile modulus. In fig. 5 all investigated unit cells as a function of the used spacings and pitch lengths are shown.

Fig. 5: Stitched unit cells of a ABC laminate depending on different stitch arrangements (68 tex stitching thread, stitched parallel to x)

In fig. 6 all results of the FE analysis are referred to experimental value of the unstitched ABC laminates (tab. 1) corresponding to both test directions (black columns). A good agreement between experiment and analysis was found for the unstitched laminates (about 4 % difference) on the tensile modulus parallel to x which is at the lower limit of the experimental scatter. On the other hand, the experimental mean of the unstitched laminate tested parallel to y show a 10 % difference to the FE analysis. The theoretical results for the stitched laminates parallel to y are within the scatter of the experimental data for the stitch arrangements $s_1;p_1$ and $s_3;p_1$.

Fig. 6: Comparison between experimental and theoretical (FE) tensile modulus of ABC laminates (68 tex stitching thread, stitching parallel to x)

The stitch arrangements $s_3;p_1$ and $s_3;p_3$ tested parallel to x as well as $s_1;p_3$ tested parallel to y show large differences between the experimental and theoretical results. One possible reason of the large differences between the experiments and the theoretical prediction may be due to some simplification introduced in the generation of the unit cell as disorientations of in-plane fibers in the vicinity of the voids were not taken into account.

CONCLUSIONS

Stitching is a very flexible method to introduce 3D reinforcements in a composite in order to enhance the mechanical out-of plane properties, to improve delamination resistance, to reduce crack propagation and, at last, to join dry semi-finished fiber products. In contrast to the positive effects due to through-the-thickness stitching it was observed that an additional yarn leads to disorientations of in-plane fibers. Changes in mechanical in-plane properties due to stitching were found in comparison to unstitched composites.

In the present work the in-plane tensile modulus of unstitched and stitched $[45/0/-45/0/90]_s$ carbon fiber NCF laminates was investigated. The composite laminates were manufactured in a vacuum assisted resin infusion process with RTM 6 epoxy resin. A full factorial experimental test series was carried out to quantify the influence of varying stitching parameters on the in-plane tensile modulus: direction of stitching and testing, thread diameter, spacing and pitch length.

It could be confirmed that additional stitching in the thickness direction in most cases reduces the in-plane tensile modulus. A maximum reduction of 29 % was found for a stitch density of $9,18 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and a thread diameter of 136 tex tested perpendicular to the direction of stitching x. In contrast to this it was observed that the in-plane tensile modulus of stitched laminates was in some cases within the scatter of the unstitched composites (e. g. stitch density of 6.06 cm^{-2} , 136 tex thread, tested perpendicular to the direction of stitching y). An analysis of variance showed that the in-plane tensile modulus is primarily affected by the stitching thread diameter as well as the interaction of the stitching thread diameter and the pitch length. Furthermore, the test direction relative to the stitch spacing show statistically significant effects. On the other hand it was found that the single parameters direction of testing and spacing between stitching lines showed no significant influence on the in-plane tensile modulus.

Following the tensile tests the formation of voids due to varying spacing and pitch length was evaluated optically. For this purpose the void cross section dependent on the stitch arrangement was analyzed in each layer of a stitched laminate (stitching parallel to x, 68 tex stitching thread). The largest voids occurred in the top and bottom surface layers of the laminate while the extension of the voids in the interior of the laminate was reduced to one-fourth. It was found that the stitch pattern significantly influences the void formation. Therefore, it was concluded that information on the orientation and the cross sectional area of voids within the individual of the laminate is essential in order to generate a unit cell model which enables the reliable estimation of the in-plane tensile modulus of stitched NCF laminates.

Finally, a finite element based unit cell model was developed which considers the influence of essential stitching parameters in terms of the resulting in-plane voids. Comparisons between experimental and theoretical results on the in-plane tensile modulus showed in general a good agreement, whereas larger deviations were found in some cases as well. Possible reasons for these discrepancies may include over simplifications in the generation of the unit cell associated with the disorientation of the in-plane fibers.

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REFERENCES

1. Cox, B. N., Flanagan, G.: Handbook of analytical methods for textile composites. NASA Contractor Report 4750, NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, Virginia (1997).
2. Dransfield, K. A., Jain, L. K., Mai, Y. W.: On the effects of stitching in CFRPs – I. Mode-I delamination Toughness. Composites Science and Technology 58 (1998), S. 815–827.

3. Mouritz, A. P., Cox, B. N.: A mechanistic approach to the properties of stitched laminates. *Composites Part A*. Vol. 31 (2000), S. 1–27.
4. Daimler-Benz-Aerospace Airbus: QVA-Z10-46-35, Bestimmung von Zugeigenschaften von CFK-Laminaten aus unidirektionalem Prepreg (Tape), Prüfung senkrecht zur Faser (90°). 1996.
5. Daimler-Benz-Aerospace Airbus: QVA-Z10-46-36, Bestimmung von Zugeigenschaften von CFK-Laminaten aus Gewebe-Prepreg, Prüfung in Kett- oder Schussrichtung. 1996.
6. Roth, Y. C., Himmel, N.: Theoretical model and experimental investigation on the effect of stitching on the in-plane stiffness of CFRP, 10th European Conference on Composite Materials, June 03–07 2002, Brugge, Belgium.
7. Krottmaier, J.: *Versuchsplanung*. Köln: Verl. Industrielle Organisation 1991.
8. Roth, Y. C., Himmel, N.: The influence of stitching on the in-plane tensile properties of non-crimp fabric laminates, 6th International Conference on Textile Composites, September 11–13 2002, Philadelphia, USA.